

Interaction between Corporate Social Responsibility, Economic Value Added and Market Value Added

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine and analyze the effect of corporate social responsibility as an independent variable on economic value added and market value added as the dependent variable and the relationship of corporate social responsibility with economic value added and market value added. The study population was 17 companies included in the type of plantation company in the observation period for 5 (five) years, namely from 2013 - 2017. This study used a purposive sampling technique to determine the research sample. The type of data used is quantitative data. The data collection method used is the archival strategy. The method used to analyze the data is to use simple linear regression with the classic assumption test and to test the hypothesis proposed using the statistical test t and Spearman correlation analysis is processed with SPSS version 25. The results of the study concluded that there was no effect of corporate social responsibility on economic value added and market value added, and no relationship was found between corporate social responsibility and economic value added and market value added.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, Economic Value Added, Market Value Added.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Plantation Company is a company in the form of a business entity/legal entity engaged in plantation cultivation activities on land it controls, for economic/commercial purposes and has obtained a business permit from the authorized agency in granting plantation business permits. Indonesia is the world's number one palm oil producing country. It is estimated that in the long term, global demand for palm oil shows an increasing trend in line with the growing world population and increasing consumption of products with palm oil as a raw material. Palm oil is one of the most widely consumed and produced oils in the world. Another type of primary plantation product is rubber. Rubber is a commodity used in many products and equipment throughout the world. International rubber prices have begun to weaken since early 2011 due to low global demand.

The growing public awareness of the environment has been supported by the Government with the issuance of Law Number 40 of 2007, as stated in Article 74 Paragraph 1 Companies that carry out their business activities in the field and/or related to natural resources are required to implement Social and Environmental Responsibility. Thus, companies in the plantation sector are required to implement corporate

social responsibility (CSR). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept where companies integrate social and environmental interests into their business operations and in their interactions with stakeholders on a voluntary basis (EU Commission, 2002 347 Final: 5). Several agricultural companies, especially plantation companies, have experienced a decline in share prices in recent years, followed by a decrease in profits earned by the company.

When profits decline, companies must strive to maintain production levels and survive, but at the same time, they must still implement CSR in accordance with laws and regulations. This can ultimately lead to a conflict of interest, where companies will cut or reduce costs deemed less significant for the company's progress during these difficult times. CSR funds, initially large when the company was at its peak, have automatically decreased in value during the current crisis. Therefore, it can be concluded that CSR is related to a company's financial performance.

The most common value-based financial performance indicator is the economic value added method, first developed by Stewart & Stern, a financial analyst from Stern Stewart & Co., in 1993. According to Tunggal (2008:2), economic value added is the profit remaining after deducting the cost of capital invested to generate that profit.

Corporate social responsibility, besides being related to a company's financial performance, is also related to the company's value in the eyes of its stakeholders. The company value chosen by researchers is market value added. According to Brigham and Houston (2010:111), "Market value added is the difference between the market value of a company's equity and the book value as presented in the balance sheet, a market value calculated by multiplying the share price by the number of shares outstanding".

The implementation of CSR in a company provides a positive signal to shareholders and stakeholders that the company is an ethical company, thus increasing the company's stock price, which in turn also increases the market value added. The difference between this study and previous studies is that the researchers examined the interaction of financial performance, company value, and corporate social responsibility. In previous studies, researchers only examined the influence or relationship of CSR with financial performance or CSR with company value separately. In addition to these differences, the existence of a research gap has made researchers interested in examining the interaction between CSR with financial performance and company value.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Stakeholder Theory

According to stakeholder theory, a company is an entity that operates not only for its own benefit but also to provide benefits to its stakeholders. Therefore, stakeholder support significantly influences a company's existence (Rosiana, 2013). This theory can be used to explain social and environmental disclosure behavior. Companies will strive to satisfy stakeholders to survive by disclosing the necessary information (Setiawati, 2013).

2.2 Signalling Theory

Signaling theory emphasizes the importance of information for investors and business actors in determining their investment decisions. The assumption of signaling theory is that parties related to a company do not have the same information regarding the company's prospects and risks (information asymmetry), where managers usually have better information than outside parties (such as investors) (Hanafi, 2013:314). CSR is closely related to signaling theory, where the implementation of CSR is considered good news for investors.

2.3 Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory is one of the theories underlying CSR disclosure. Companies implement CSR programs in the hope of gaining positive value and legitimacy from society. This means that if a company gains

legitimacy from society, it can continue to survive and thrive within the community, generating profits in the future (Khoirudin, 2013). In Indonesia, the implementation of CSR is mandatory under Law Number 40 of 2007, as stipulated in Article 74 Paragraph 1: Companies conducting business in the field of and/or related to natural resources are required to implement Social and Environmental Responsibility.

2.4 Corporate Social Responsibility

At a meeting in Brussels in 2002, the Commission of the European Communities defined CSR as a concept where companies integrate social and environmental concerns into their business operations and interactions with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis.

2.5 Economic Value Added

EVA is the value added to shareholders by management during a given year. Economic value added focuses on managerial effectiveness (Brigham, 2001:51). According to Tunggal (2008:2), economic value added is the profit remaining after deducting the cost of capital invested to generate that profit. Economic value added is a value-based measure of financial performance. It describes the absolute amount of shareholder value created or destroyed over a specific period, usually one year. According to Hanafi (2013:52), "Economic value added is a performance measure that combines the value gained with the cost of that added value".

2.6 Market Value Added

According to Brigham and Houston (2010:111), "Market value added is the difference between the market value of a company's equity and its book value, as presented in the balance sheet. Market value is calculated by multiplying the share price by the number of shares outstanding." Maximizing shareholder wealth is the goal of financial decision-making. Shareholder wealth will increase if market value added increases. Shareholder wealth is maximized by maximizing the difference between the market value of equity and the equity (equity) invested by investors.

Based on the description of the literature above, the hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows.

H1: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has an impact on Economic Value Added (EVA).

H2: Economic Value Added (EVA) influences Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

H3: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has an impact on Market Value Added (MVA).

H4: Market Value Added (MVA) influences Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted to determine the interaction between CSR, EVA, and MVA. The type of research is explanatory research, outlining existing theories and testing or developing them (Neuman, 2013: 45). The population of this study were plantation companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2013-2017. The sampling technique was purposive sampling, resulting in a sample of 40 companies over a five-year period. The data type is quantitative. The data used in this study are

secondary data taken from the Company's Annual Report. The data collection technique is an archival strategy. The indicators used for each latent variable in this study include:

- Corporate Social Responsibility variable with GRI G4 indicator.
- Financial Performance variable with Economic Value Added (EVA) ratio.
- Company Values variable with Market Value Added (MVA) ratio.

4. RESULT

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Based on the available and processed data, the following are descriptive statistics for each variable in the study:

Tabel 1. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CSR	40	.0879	.7363	.261538	.1451726
EVA	40	-490838556251	27806160096	-147268054737.29	144821790933.128
MVA	40	-407372080000	38655123500000	8496031611512.53	9331247413502.230
Valid N (listwise)	40				

Before conducting a hypothesis test, a classical assumption test will be carried out first, consisting of a normality test, a multicollinearity test, a heteroscedasticity test, and an autocorrelation test.

Tabel 2. Uji one sample test Kolmogorov-smirnov

Hipotesis	Uraian	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	N	Kesimpulan
H ₁	Unstandardized Residual	0,137	0,055	40	Terdistribusi normal
H ₂	Unstandardized Residual	0,256	0,000	40	Tidak terdistribusi normal
H ₃	Unstandardized Residual	0,240	0,000	40	Tidak terdistribusi normal
H ₄	Unstandardized Residual	0,255	0,000	40	Tidak terdistribusi normal

Sumber : Data diolah kembali, 2019

The results of the study using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test method show that in hypothesis 1 the probability value of $asymp.sig (2-tailed) > 0.05$ is 0.055, this means that the residual data is normally distributed, while in hypothesis 2, 3 and 4 the probability value of $asymp.sig (2-$

$tailed) < 0.05$, this means that the residual data is not normally distributed. To obtain the best results, outlier data is removed with a boxplot, so that the company sample becomes 31 companies. After removing the outlier data, a

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second normality test is carried out, so that the results of the K-S test are obtained as follows:

Tabel 2. Uji one sample test Kolmogorov-smirnov

Hipotesis	Uraian	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	N	Kesimpulan
H ₁	Unstandardized Residual	0,130	0,193	31	Terdistribusi normal
H ₂	Unstandardized Residual	0,061	0,200	31	Terdistribusi normal
H ₃	Unstandardized Residual	0,109	0,200	31	Terdistribusi normal
H ₄	Unstandardized Residual	0,109	0,200	31	Terdistribusi normal

Sumber : Data diolah kembali, 2019

The results of the second test indicate that the data are normally distributed for all hypotheses. This is demonstrated by the Kormogorov-Smirnov test, which shows an asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) probability value > 0.05.

Tabel 3. Hasil Uji Multikolonieritas

Hipotesis	Variabel	Collinearity Statistics		Kesimpulan
		Tolerance	VIF	
H ₁	Corporate Social Responsibility	1,000	1,000	Tidak terjadi multikolonieritas
H ₂	Economic value added	1,000	1,000	Tidak terjadi multikolonieritas
H ₃	Corporate Social Responsibility	1,000	1,000	Tidak terjadi multikolonieritas
H ₄	Market value added	1,000	1,000	Tidak terjadi multikolonieritas

Sumber : Data diolah kembali, 2019

The calculation results in Table 3 show that the tolerance value shows that no independent variables have a tolerance value of less than 0.10, which means there is no correlation between the independent variables with a value greater than 95%. The calculation results for the variance inflation factor

(VIF) also show the same thing, that none of the independent variables have a VIF value greater than 10, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

Tabel 4. Hasil Uji Heteroskedastisitas

Hipotesis	Variabel	Sig	Kesimpulan
H ₁	Corporate Social Responsibility	0,760	Tidak terjadi heteroskedastisitas
H ₂	Economic value added	0,302	Tidak terjadi heteroskedastisitas
H ₃	Corporate Social Responsibility	0,840	Tidak terjadi heteroskedastisitas
H ₄	Market value added	0,963	Tidak terjadi heteroskedastisitas

Sumber : Data diolah kembali, 2019

The coefficients for the beta parameters of the regression equation in Table 4 are not significant because the sig value is > 0.05. This can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Tabel 5. Hasil Uji Durbin-Watson

Var. Dependen	Var. Independen	Adjusted R Square	Durbin-Watson	Kesimpulan
Economic value added	Corporate social responsibility	0,178	2,317	Tidak ada autokorelasi
Corporate social responsibility	Economic value added	0,178	2,379	Tidak ada autokorelasi
Market value added	Corporate social responsibility	-0,036	1,840	Tidak ada autokorelasi
Corporate social responsibility	Market value added	-0,036	2,346	Tidak ada autokorelasi

Sumber : Data diolah kembali, 2019

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The autocorrelation test that has been carried out produces Durbin Watson numbers as in table 5 and after being compared with the Durbin Watson table, it can be concluded that no autocorrelation occurs.

Tabel 6. Hasil Uji t

Hipotesis	Koefisien			Sig	t	Kesimpulan
	Determinasi (R Square)	Konstanta	Beta			
H ₁	0,178	-3,553E ¹¹	1,139E ¹²	0,011	2,734	Berpengaruh Positif
H ₂	0,178	0,221	1,800E ⁻¹³	0,011	2,734	Berpengaruh Positif
H ₃	-0,036	29,438	-0,153	0,963	-0,047	Tidak Berpengaruh
H ₄	0,000	0,212	-0,001	0,963	-0,047	Tidak Berpengaruh

Sumber : Data yang diolah kembali, 2019

Hypothesis testing was conducted using a t-test. The t-test results are presented in Table 6. The significance values for Hypotheses 1 and 2 were below 0.05, indicating that both hypotheses were accepted. The implementation of CSR by a company will have a positive impact on its financial performance. This is in line with signaling theory, where CSR disclosure is positive information that is responded to positively by stakeholders, thereby improving the company's financial performance. Improved financial performance should also lead to increased budget allocations for CSR implementation. Because companies have already implemented CSR initiatives, they will have no objections to allocating budgets for CSR implementation. This is supported by legitimacy theory and Law Number 40 of 2007, which requires companies involved in environmental issues to implement social and environmental responsibilities. The significance value for hypothesis 3 and 4 is above 0.05 which means that both hypotheses are rejected. The results of this study if associated with the legitimacy theory that corporate social responsibility is only to maintain harmonization between the company and its stakeholders, carry out the obligation to implement CSR and maintain the company's image without real realization for social welfare and the surrounding environment, so that the company cannot feel the benefits of implementing CSR that it does, in addition investors have difficulty in finding CSR disclosures carried out by the company in the annual report, even though it has been reported but the quality of reporting and clarity of information is not too good, so that in increasing the company's stock price, investors only tend to pay attention to the profits generated by the company, stock returns and dividends.

5. CONCLUSION

5.1 Conclusion

This study aims to determine the interaction between corporate social responsibility, economic value added, and market value added using a sample of plantation companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. Based on the above research results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Corporate social responsibility has a positive effect on economic value added.

- Economic value added has a positive effect on corporate social responsibility.
- There is an interaction between corporate social responsibility and economic value added in plantation companies from 2013 to 2017.
- Corporate social responsibility has no effect on market value added.
- Market value added has no positive effect on corporate social responsibility.
- There is no interaction between corporate social responsibility and market value added in plantation companies from 2013 to 2017.

This study has limitations, including the lack of specific regulations governing company annual reports and corporate social responsibility disclosures in Indonesia, which means GRI-G4 disclosures are still suboptimal. The study sample consisted of only a relatively small number of plantation companies, and the study period was relatively short, at five years. Some suggestions proposed from the results of this study are that future research can use research samples that are also closely related to environmental issues, such as mining or basic industries and chemicals. Furthermore, further research can use other financial performance variables to test the interaction with CSR. The government is expected to immediately issue specific regulations or rules that govern the implementation of corporate social responsibility clearly and in detail, and companies can improve disclosure of corporate social responsibility implementation in accordance with applicable standards, which can use GRI-G4, ISO 26000, or other global standards.

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